

A Study on ANODR and HEAP Protocol in MANET

S. Victor Samuel¹, S. Peter²

^{1,2} System Analyst, Chennai Engineering Service, Chennai, Tamilnadu, India. E-mail: svictor_27@rediff.com

Abstract – An ad hoc network is a group of wireless mobile computers, in which individual nodes cooperate by forwarding packets for each other to allow nodes to communicate beyond direct wireless transmission range. Routing in wireless ad hoc networks are vulnerable to traffic analysis, address spoofing attack due to open wireless medium communication. In a mobile network, a node's motion pattern, traffic pattern, standing venue, route-driven packet flows, and even the dynamic network topology can be traced by any malicious node. In order to defend against anonymity threats, Anonymous On -demand routing Protocol (ANODR) was developed which basically works on the two design principles such as an identity free and on-demand routing scheme. ANODR uses identity free approach. It means that instead of using node identities it uses cryptographic techniques. ANODR is purely on-demand routing schemes that set up route as and when needed. This limits the chance of eavesdropping and traffic analysis. But still it's possible to launch various attacks such as wormhole, man-in-the-middle and Denial of Service (DOS), or to impersonate another node. To combat such attacks from outsider nodes, Hop-by-Hop Efficient Authentication Protocol called HEAP was proposed. In this paper, a study of ANODR and HEAP protocol are done and security analysis and simulation study verifies the efficiency and effectiveness of ANODR and HEAP protocol.

Keywords: ANODR, HEAP, Onion Routing, MANET

I. Introduction

MANET's are a new paradigm of wireless wearable devices enabling instantaneous person-to-person, person-to-machine or machine-to-person immediately and easily. Possible commercial applications include business associates sharing information during a meeting, students using laptop computers to participate in an interactive lecture, and emergency disaster relief personnel coordinating efforts in natural disasters. Applications such as military exercises, disaster relief may benefit from ad hoc networking. In these applications, where a fixed backbone is not available, a readily deployable wireless network is needed. Mobile ad hoc networks are also a good alternative in rural areas where basic communication infrastructure is not well established. Another interesting application of mobile ad hoc networks is ubiquitous computing. Intelligent devices are connected with one another via wireless links and are self-organized in such a way that a newly joined node can request service from local servers without any human intervention.

When designing mobile ad hoc networks, several interesting and difficult problems arise due to shared nature of the wireless medium, limited transmission power (range) of wireless devices, node mobility, and battery limitations. The limited transmission range of wireless network interfaces coupled with the highly dynamic routing infrastructure, due to mobility, create a lot of concerns when addressing issues such as dynamic routing, efficient channel access and quality-of-service

(QoS) support. Wired network routing protocols do not handle well the type of rapid node mobility and network topology changes that occur in ad hoc networks. Due to node mobility and open wireless transmissions it is vulnerable to security threats. When addressing the issues of dynamic routing, it creates a lot of concerns such as identity privacy, message privacy and anonymity issues. A node in a network has anonymity property if no other node can identify the identity of previous nodes. This property is very useful for the secured routing in the mobile adhoc network.

ANODR uses identity free approach, instead of using node identities it uses cryptographic techniques so that only receiver can decrypt the message using its private key. ANODR is purely on-demand routing schemes that set up route as when needed. This limits the chance of eavesdropping and traffic analysis. ANODR protocol used to combat against insider attack, but it does not provide solution for outsider attacks such as wormhole, man-in-the-middle and Denial of Service (DOS), or to impersonate another node. To defend against such attacks, Hop-by-Hop Efficient Authentication Protocol called HEAP was proposed.

In this paper, performance study of ANODR and HEAP protocol are done and security analysis and simulation study verifies the efficiency and effectiveness of ANODR and HEAP protocol. By measuring metrics such as latency, throughput, packet delivery ratio, cpu and memory utilization HEAP performs very well while guarding against outsider attack.

II. Routing Protocol

Mobility support relies on the existence of at least some infrastructure as discussed in [3] Mobile communications, there may be situations where users of a network cannot rely on an infrastructure, it's too expensive, or there is none at all. In these situations mobile ad hoc networks are the only choice. Routing is needed to find the path between source and destination and to forward the packets appropriately. There are mainly two types of Routing protocol, proactive and reactive protocols. Proactive protocol set up tables required for routing regardless of any traffic .A big disadvantage of proactive scheme are their overheads in lightly loaded networks. Independent of any real communication the algorithm continuously updates the routing tables. This generates a lot of unnecessary traffic and drains the batteries of mobile devices. Reactive protocols try to avoid this problem by setting up a path between sender and receiver only if a communication is waiting.

III. Security in Routing Protocol

On demand routing is used in proposals such as [1] ODAR (On-Demand Anonymous Routing) and [2] ANODR (Anonymous On-Demand Routing) in Ad Hoc networks. ODAR is a reactive protocol, which set up the route as when needed. ODAR enable complete anonymity of nodes, links, and source –routing paths. Anonymity that hides the identities of various components or parts of a network communications is one of the countermeasures. Strong anonymity in network communication prevents address spoofing, route forgery, and certain denial of services. ANODR works on the two design principles such as an identity free and on-demand routing scheme. To prevent this, ANODR uses identity free approach, instead of using node identities it uses cryptographic techniques so that only receiver can decrypt the message using its private key. ANODR is purely on-demand routing schemes that set up route as when needed .This limits the chance of eavesdropping and traffic analysis.

To establish anonymous route in ODAR and ANODR, onion routing is used [4]. Onion routing for anonymous communication uses cryptographic algorithms. In Onion routing, to construct an anonymous path, a packet origin must store and maintain information about the topology of the onion router network, out of which a number of Onion routers are selected by the packet origin to construct the path. In addition, each node on the path is supplied with a symmetric key for encrypting and decrypting data packets, and getting instructions for the next hop router in the path. When a data packet is ready to send, the source recursively encrypts the packet and the next hop information with the symmetric keys along the path. This creates a layered structure, in which it is

necessary to decrypt all outer layers of the onion in order to retrieve an inner layer.

In order to provide security the data is being sent in encrypted form and decrypted at the receiver side which provides additional security.[6] Cryptography and network security proposed many algorithms. Cryptography plays an important role in the security of data. It enables us to store sensitive information or transmit it across insecure networks so that unauthorized persons cannot read it. Symmetric keys algorithm executes faster. AES (Advanced Encryption Standard) is a symmetric block cipher uses secret key shared between the source and the destination.

The goal of the [5] HEAP (Hop- by –hop Efficient Authentication Protocol for Mobile Ad hoc Networks) is thwart attacks from outsider nodes.. HEAP authenticates packets at every hop and drops packets that originate from any outsiders. The outsider node has the capability to spoof the node identities to impersonate an insider node. HEAP authenticates control as well as data packets

IV. Onion Routing

Onion Routing is a practical real-time bi-directional application-independent Mix-based infrastructure for private communication over a public network. It strongly resists traffic analysis, eavesdropping, and other attacks both by outsiders (e.g. Internet routers) and insiders (Onion Routers themselves). It hides the identities of the communication's parties and its content. The purpose is not to hide the sender and the receiver identities from each other, but to protect their communication from others.

Fig. 1 Onion Routing Protocol

It works in the following way: The sender makes a connection to an onion router. The onion router builds a chain of onion routers to the receiver. Each onion router in that chain can only identify his immediate onion router neighbors. To send data, the first onion router creates encryption layers for all onion routers in the chain and adds these layers to the data. After adding the encryption layers to the data, it is sent through the next onion routers. Each onion router, when receiving the encrypted

packet, removes one encryption layer, so the data arrives decrypted to the receiver. As a consequence of the layering, data appears different at each onion router, so it cannot be tracked and onion routers cannot maliciously collaborate.

V. Conclusion

Anonymous On-Demand Routing (ANODR) uses two design principles i.e. Identity free and On-Demand Routing which provides security against compromised node, passive attack and relies only on efficient symmetric cryptography. But HEAP provides authentication for each forwarding node in the network and it provides more secure transmission between the source and the destination against active attackers. It provides better security for transferring the data packets among the nodes in the mobile ad hoc network.

References

- [1] B. Dahill, B. Levine, E. Royer, and C. Shields, "A Secure Routing Protocol for Ad Hoc Networks", University of Massachusetts Technical Report 01-37, 2001, Denh Sy, Rex Chen and Lichun Bao, "On-Demand Anonymous Routing in Ad Hoc networks".
- [2] C. Perkins, E. Belding-Royer, and S. Das, "Ad hoc On-Demand Distance Vector (AODV) Routing," RFC 3561, July 2003
- [3] Denh Sy, Rex Chen and Lichun Bao, "On-Demand Anonymous Routing in Ad Hoc networks", *proc INFOCOM*, 2005.
- [4] Jiejun kong, Xiaoyan Hong, and Mario Gerla, "An Identity-Free and On-Demand Routing Scheme against Anonymity Threats in Mobile Ad hoc Networks", *proc MobileHoc*, pp 291-302, 2003.
- [5] Marc O' Morian, Vladislav Titov and Wendy Verbuggen "Onion Routing for anonymous communication", *proc IEEE Int'l conf network protocols [Icnp '02]* 2002.
- [6] Rehan Akbani, Turgay Korkmaz and G.V.S Raju "Hop-by-hop Efficient Authentication Protocol for Mobile Adhoc Networks" University of Texas at San Antonio, 2007
- [7] D. Chaum. "The Dining Cryptographers Problem: Unconditional Sender and Recipient Untraceability", *Journal of Cryptology* 1:65-75, 1988
- [8] D. Chaum. "Untraceable Electronic Mail, Return Addresses, and Digital Pseudonyms", *Communication of the ACM*, v. 24, n. 2, Feb. 1981, pp.84-88.
- [9] Marc O' Morian, Vladislav Titov and Wendy Verbuggen "Onion Routing fo Jiejun Kong, Xiaoyan Hong, ANODR: anonymous on demand routing with untraceable routes for mobile ad-hoc networks, Proceedings of the 4th ACM international symposium on Mobile ad hoc networking & computing, June 01-03, 2003, Annapolis, Maryland, USA [doi>10.1145/778415.778449]
- [10] M. Reed, P. Syverson, and D. Goldschlag. "Anonymous Connections and Onion Routing", *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, vol. 16, no. 4, May 1998, pp. 482-494.
- [12] M. Reed, P. Syverson, and D. Goldschlag "Onion Routing Access Configuration", *DISCEX 2000: Proceedings of the DARPA Information Survivability Conference and Exposition, Volume I* Hilton Head, SC, IEEE CS Press, January 2000, pp. 34-40
- [13] M. K. Reiter and A. D. Rubin. "Crowds: Anonymity for Web Transactions", *ACM Transactions on Information and System Security*, vol. 1, no. 1, November 1998, pp. 66-92.
- [14] R. Song, L. Korba, and G. Yee. AnonDSR: Efficient Anonymous Dynamic Source Routing for Mobile Ad-Hoc Networks. In *ACM Workshop on Security of Ad Hoc and Sensor Networks (SASN)*, 2005.